

Study of Magnesium Tartrate Crystals by Sol Gel Method

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Abstract:

In the present study, single crystals of magnesium tartrate crystals were grown by using silica gel as a growth medium. These crystals were grown by simple sol gel technique using diffusion method. The optimum growth conditions for these crystals were optimized by varying various process parameters. The shiny white coloured and spherulitic morphology crystals grown within silica gel column were obtained. The crystalline nature of grown crystal was confirmed by using powder X-ray diffraction technique which shows that magnesium tartrate hydrate has crystallized in orthorhombic structure. The functional groups present in the crystals were identified by using FTIR analysis which shows that the presence of O = H, C = O, C – O, C – H and metal – oxygen bonds. The SEM study reveals that the morphology of the crystal having orthorhombic structures. The analysis of EDAX has shown the presence of Magnesium and Oxygen.

Keywords: Magnesium Tartrate, XRD, FTIR, SEM, EDAX.

Introduction:

Crystal habit of various crystals, grown under different conditions and also by different methods viz., melt growth, vapour phase growth, solution growth and gel growth were described by H. E. Buckley [1], P. Hartman [2], K. Kern [3], A. A. Chernov [4], W. K. Burton [5] and J. Mullin [6]. A number of factors such as concentration of reactants, pH of gel [7, 8], impurities in the solvent [9], gel setting time and gel aging time etc. have considerable effect on growth rate. In the steady state of concentration gradient, growth rate also becomes steady which favors growth of well-developed crystals [10]. However, very slow rate of growth along one direction results in the platy crystals and spherulitic crystals.

Crystals are the backbone of the revolution of modern science and technology [11-13]. At the beginning the base of gel growth techniques for low solubility crystals has been established and afterwards, such methods of crystal growth were applied to soluble materials with a low molecular

weight. The Moirer and Vesque was the first researcher, who records the growth of large crystals by slow diffusion in gel. A systematic study of crystallization in gels begins with Lissegang's famous discovery of periodic crystallization in gels. This method has gained considerable attention because of its simplicity and effectiveness in growing single crystal of certain compound. This technique is an alternative technique to solution growth with controlled diffusion. This growth process is free from convection. This is purifying process, free from thermal strain [14-20].

Growth and Characterization of some tartrate crystals were reported by Henisch and Henisch et al [21], Patel and Rao [22]. Growth of some crystals of tartrate compounds like calcium tartrate [23, 24], strontium tartrate [25], barium tartrate [26, 27], ammonium tartrate [28], zinc tartrate [29], sodium tartrate [30], cadmium tartrate [31] and iron tartrate [32] were reported by earlier researchers. The compounds of Tartaric acid find

numerous applications in semiconductor and optics industries with the invention of lasers. The field of non-linear optics touched the new heights and practical implementations were possible with the various applications of non-linear optical crystals [33]. Many of the tartrate compounds including pure and mixed tartrate deserve special attention due to its medical, pharmaceutical and industrial applications such as, injections of Na-Cr tartrate increase the susceptibility of the transplanted sarcoma to the effect of X-rays, calciphylactic responses of various ferrous tartrate compounds to prevent anemia in animals, ferrous tartrate as a catalyst in manufacture of champagne, tanning action of ferrous tartrate to tan skin, the use of manganese tartrate crystals in chemical temperature indicators, strontium tartrate used in ammunition units, zinc tartrate with other compounds form a bright coating and used as protecting powder for metals etc.[34-37].

In the present investigation, single crystals of magnesium tartrate were grown by a simple gel technique using diffusion method. The optimum conditions were established by varying various process parameters such as pH, concentration gel solution, setting time of the gel solution and concentration of the reactance. The optimum growth conditions for these crystals were determined. These crystals were characterized by using XRD, FTIR, SEM and EDAX.

Experimental:

Magnesium Tartrate ($C_4H_4MgO_6$) crystals were grown by single diffusion method in silica gel medium at room temperature. The Sodium Meta Silicate (Na_2SiO_3) solution and acetic acid (CH_3COOH) was prepared by dissolving 22gm (Na_2SiO_3) into the 250ml distilled water and 15ml (CH_3COOH) dissolving into 250ml distilled water respectively. Then (Na_2SiO_3) was added into 6ml (CH_3COOH) drop by drop by maintaining the pH

4.2 with continues till the solution becomes milky. After that 15ml solution of Magnesium chloride ($MgCl_2$) with 1M added into the gel solution. This mixture was then transferred to the test tube of 15 cm × 2.5 cm dimension. After setting the gel in 4-5 days, the 10ml tartaric acid ($C_4H_6O_6$) with 1M was allow to fall steadily along the wall of the tube above the set gel, next day the small nucleation growth was observed at below the interface of gel. This nucleation growth was increased in size. The chemical reaction inside the gel can be expressed as follows:

Good quality shiny white coloured spherulitic crystals were grown in 45-48 days. The crystalline nature of grown crystals was confirmed using powder X-ray diffraction technique. The functional groups present in the single crystals were identified using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis. The SEM was done to find the structural morphology of the grown crystals. The presence of magnesium and oxygen was confirmed by EDAX analysis.

Results and Discussion:

The Fig. 1 shows the crystals of magnesium tartrate attached themselves and forming a thick layer at the interface whereas Fig. 2 shows a few grown crystals of magnesium tartrate having different habits with their scaling on a graph paper. The grown crystals are of the 3.5mm × 3.5mm × 2.5mm size. The various optimum conditions for growing crystals were established and are given in the Table 1. For pH 4.2 the spherulitic crystals were observed in the interface of the gel column [21]. Tartaric acid

($C_4H_6O_6$) used as upper reactant. Gel age is the time interval between gel and pouring of the upper reactant.

Fig.1 shows the grown magnesium tartrate crystals.

Fig. 2 shows the shiny white coloured magnesium tartrate crystals.

Table 1 Optimum condition for growth of magnesium tartrate crystals.

Conditions for growth of magnesium tartrate crystals	Single diffusion
Density of sodium meta silicate (Na_2SiO_3)	1.05 gm/cm ³
Amount of 1M acetic acid(CH_3COOH)	6 ml
pH of the gel	4.2
Temperature	Room Temperature
Concentration of Magnesium Chloride ($MgCl_2$)	15 ml
Concentration of 1M Tartaric acid($C_4H_6O_6$)	10 ml
Gel setting period	4-5 days
Gel aging period	24 Hrs
Growth of period	45- 48 days
Quality	Shiny white, Large size, Spherulitic morphology
Size of Crystals	3.5mm × 3.5mm × 2.5mm

Powder X-ray diffraction analysis of magnesium tartrate crystals

Fig. 3 XRD pattern of magnesium tartrate crystals.

The crystal structure of the sample compound was studied by powder X-ray diffraction method. The X-ray diffraction was recorded using Bruker-D8 Advance, Germany (2θ from 5° to 80°) with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation of wavelength $\lambda=1.54060\text{\AA}$. The X-ray diffraction technique is used to investigate the inner arrangement of atoms or molecules in a crystalline material. The recorded X-ray diffraction of the magnesium tartrate crystals is shown in the Fig. 3. The analysis of different diffraction peaks indicates the formation of orthorhombic structure [22]. The crystalline phases and d-values obtained from the XRD have been compared with the JCPDS data from X'Pert High Score PANalytical software. The XRD pattern of Fig. 4 matches with the JCPDS files 00-001-0225 and 00-023-0390, indicating that the sample consisted of magnesium tartrate crystalline.

Fig. 4 Shows graphics of the X-ray powder diffraction pattern of magnesium tartrate by X'Pert High Score PANalytical Software.

The grain size is determined by measuring the width of the line with each intensity peaks and then the average grain size have been obtained from the XRD pattern using the Scherrer's calculator from X'Pert High Score software [33]. The obtained average grain size of magnesium tartrate crystals is 0.60 nm. The values of 2θ , d-values, intensity and h k l values are shown in the Table 2.

Table 2 Powder X-ray diffraction data of magnesium tartrate crystals ($\lambda=1.54060\text{\AA}$).

Observed data values			Standard data values			h k l values	Matched by X'Pert HighScore PANalytical Software
2θ	d-value	Intensity	2θ	d-value	Rel. Intensity		
13.692	6.46206	467	13.6735	6.47625	56.32	010	00-001-0225
16.750	5.28857	383	16.7750	5.28520	46.10	110	00-001-0225
23.814	3.73353	448	23.8216	3.73537	50.91	210	00-001-0225
25.187	3.53298	368	25.2839	3.52254	37.66	201	00-023-0390
27.619	3.22717	450	27.6262	3.22898	51.26	020	00-001-0225
28.284	3.15277	391	28.3017	3.15343	47.14	211	00-023-0390
32.415	2.75980	457	32.4121	2.76230	53.60	310	00-001-0225

37.760	2.38052	400	37.7448	2.38340	47.94	221	00-001-0225; 00-023-0390
39.561	2.27619	311	39.5556	2.27836	36.44	400	00-001-0225
40.800	2.20988	113	40.8036	2.21151	11.50	320	00-023-0390
50.032	1.82161	122	49.9636	1.82543	15.76	203	00-023-0390

It shows the well-defined diffraction peaks with indexed peaks, which indicate that the grown material has good crystalline nature. The obtained values of lattice parameters, viz., a, b, c and α , β , γ as well as crystal structure, lattice type were shown in the Table 3. From the powder XRD pattern, it is confirmed that grown crystal has orthorhombic structure [42].

Table 3 Lattice parameters for magnesium tartrate crystal.

Lattice Parameters	Values
a	9.14 Å
b	6.49 Å
c	5.96 Å
$\alpha=\beta=\gamma$	90°
Crystal family	Orthorhombic
Lattice Type	Primitive (P)

FTIR analysis of magnesium tartrate crystals:

The Fig. 5 shows the FTIR spectrum of the magnesium tartrate. The FTIR spectrum was recorded using Shimadzu FTIR-8400, Japan (400 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1}). The absorption peaks positioned in between 3373.61–2297.30 cm^{-1} corresponds to symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of O-H bond due to water of crystallization. The peak at 1604.83 cm^{-1} is the band corresponding to carbonyl C=O group. The band at 1303.92 cm^{-1} is the band corresponding

C-O stretching vibration. The band at 1107.18–918.15 cm^{-1} is the bands corresponding to O-H stretching out of plane vibrations. The band observed at 725.26–464.86 cm^{-1} corresponds to metal oxygen bonding [10-13].

Fig. 5 FTIR spectrum of magnesium tartrate crystals (pH 4.2).

SEM analysis of magnesium tartrate crystals:

The Fig. 6 shows the SEM image of magnesium tartrate. The FESEM image was recorded using Hitachi S-4800, Japan with X-Flash detector-5030, Bruker, Germany. The scanning electron microscope reveals that the morphology of the crystal having rectangular shape, triangular shape, looks like cubes of different shapes and sizes of orthorhombic structures [14]

Fig. 6 SEM images of magnesium tartrate crystals.

EDAX analysis of magnesium tartrate crystals:

Fig. 7 Shows the EDAX pattern of magnesium tartrate crystals. The elemental analysis of gel grown magnesium tartrate crystals was carried out by using X-Flash-60 Bruker instrument. Magnesium tartrate is one of the most complex systems with many phases and unique chemical composition as it is amplified between silica gel by the distribution of

magnesium chloride in the gel. The diversity in the stoichiometry of magnesium tartrate poses a challenge for the control of size and shape. The energy dispersive x-ray spectrum has shown that the Mg and O are present in the atomic percentage of 9.13 and 54.85 and weight percentage of 14.49 and 57.27 respectively. Table 4 shows the EDAX analysis for magnesium tartrate crystal.

Fig.7 Shows the EDAX pattern of magnesium tartrate crystals.

Table 4 EDAX analysis for magnesium tartrate crystal.

El	AN	Series	unn. C [wt. %]	norm. C [wt. %]	Atom. C [at. %]	Error (1 Sigma) [wt. %]
C	6	K-series	15.20	28.24	36.02	4.38
O	8	K-series	30.83	57.27	54.85	6.20
Mg	12	K-series	7.80	14.49	9.13	0.54
Total:			53.83	100.00	100.00	

Conclusions:

Sol gel method is found to be suitable for growing the magnesium tartrate crystals. Single diffusion method is convenient for the growth of the magnesium tartrate crystals. Nucleation control can be achieved by changing a various gel parameters such as pH of gel, density of gel and concentration of feed solutions. The shiny white spherulitic crystals were observed. The crystalline phases and d-values obtained from the XRD have been compared with the JCPDS data from X'Pert High score PANalytical software. XRD pattern shows very sharp peaks having high intensity, indicating perfect crystallization. Unit cell parameter values and d values match very well with the JCPDS data and the structure of magnesium tartrate is orthorhombic. From the FTIR spectroscopic study, the presence of O=H, C=O, C-O, C-H and metal-oxygen bonds were confirmed. The SEM study reveals that the morphology of the crystal having orthorhombic structures. The analysis of EDAX has shown anhydrous nature of the magnesium tartrate crystal with the presence of magnesium and oxygen.

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